

Editorial

Naga Performing Arts and Oral Traditions: Between Tradition and Modernity

Christian Poske

This special issue of *The Highlander Journal* is largely dedicated to the topics of Naga performing arts and oral traditions. As such, it reflects a flourishing strand of research that has established itself at the Highland Institute in recent years. The contributors of this issue are based in Hyderabad and Kiphire (India) and Boumerdes (Algeria), and their articles thematise different aspects of Naga traditional and contemporary performing arts and oral traditions, as well as a recent publication by an Indian-born Scottish poet. Considering emic and etic representations of modern Naga history, Rhelo Kenye examines Naga rapper Moko Koza's song *Boy from the Hills* (2023), concerning the experiences of Naga elders during World War II, including those of his nonagenarian grandmother Terilhuo-ü Ladu, featured in the song video and, together with Koza, on the cover of this issue. Wapanginla Aier and Anish Koshy take a linguistic approach by examining word formation processes in Poetic Mongsen, a variant of the Mongsen language used for renditions of Ao Naga traditional songs, ballads, and folk narratives. Yihingle Ndang discusses the upbringing of Zeme women who grew up in female dormitories of their communities, and the significance of their contributions to the intergenerational transmission of Zeme songs and oral narratives. Lastly, Lynda Chouiten reviews Indian-born Scottish writer Bashabi Fraser's poetry collection *Habitat* (2023), concerning the endangered diversity of the life worlds of human and non-human inhabitants of our planet. Thus, the articles included in this issue encompass a vast thematic spectrum ranging from Indigenous performing arts and oral traditions to contemporary ecological concerns, providing a link to the topics of traditional Indigenous knowledge and global environmental humanities that constituted the thematic focus of the previous issue of *The Highlander Journal*. Currently, the intersection of these interrelated domains leads to some of the most innovative and productive research at the Highland Institute, and it will certainly provide inspiring outputs for many more issues of the journal that are yet to appear.

Christian Poske, Managing Editor

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